

Comparative Analysis Between Quality Assurance Mechanisms and Administration at Secondary School Level of Education in North-West, Nigeria

*Akinsola, Olakunle S.¹

Email: femikunle2006@yahoo.com

Tel: 08035144716

Saidu, Aminu¹

Email: aminusaidu1203@gmail.com

Tel: 08031805876

Nigerian Educational Research & Development Council (NERDC), Sheda-Abuja.

Abstract

There are evidences of different views on the relationship between the various mechanism of quality assurance and school administration. Hence, this study examined the Co-relationships between Quality Assurance Mechanisms and administration at secondary school level of Education in North-west, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlation type of research design. Simple and stratified random sampling procedures were used to select the sample of the study. The population of the study consisted of 26,048 teachers from all the senior secondary schools in the North West, zone of Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample comprises of 1500 teachers from 75 secondary schools. Quality Assurance Mechanism Questionnaire (QAMQ), School Effectiveness Questionnaire (SEQ) and Qualifying Examinations results of the students were used to collect data for the study. The QAMQ and SEQ instruments were validated, and test-retest method of reliability was used to determine their reliability coefficients of 0.78 and 0.81 respectively. Two research questions guided the conduct of the study. The data collected for the study were analyzed using relevant descriptive (frequency counts and percentage score) and inferential (Pearson Product Moment Correlation) statistical tools. The study revealed a positive correlation between quality assurance mechanism, instructional supervision (0.745), in-service training (0.682), learning environment (0.825) and school administration. The study concludes that quality assurance mechanisms relate to the effectiveness administration of the schools. Therefore, it was recommended among others that the principals of the schools should sustain the tempo of supervision in schools in order to ensure better school administration.

Keywords: Education, Quality Assurance Mechanism and administration.

Introduction

Education which is a vital factor in economic and political development of any country is a process of acquiring the necessary skills needed to live a useful life as a member of the society where one lives. In any organization performing a given task, especially those engaged in human capital development like secondary schools, are in need of quality assurances. Quality assurance involves the achievement of educational programme standards which are established by institutions, professional organizations, and government. While quality assurance mechanisms are the processes by which the achievement of these standards is measured. Smith (2021) defined quality assurance as a planned and systematic review process of an institution or program to determine whether or not acceptable standards of education, scholarship, and infrastructure are being met, maintained and enhanced. Mensah, Okyere & Kuranchie, (2013) opined that quality assurance involves the evaluation of a system or a school and its operations against certain prescribed standards for self-assurance that ensure all devices are working to make output or results correspond to set objectives. Within the context of teaching and learning, quality assurance refers to the process of ensuring that practices and procedures or actions intended to enhance quality and excellence in the key areas of classroom lesson delivery and test administration are complied with. In the view expressed by Okeke-James, Igbokwe, Anyanwu, & Ogbo, (2020), quality assurance is the process of ensuring that the learners are maximally imparted with the skill and knowledge as was stated in national educational goals. Therefore, the increasing awareness of the importance of education to the upliftment of the individual and the society has made both the household and the nation devote a reasonable proportion of their earnings to acquiring qualitative education. Scheerens, (2016) defines school efficacy as the ability of a school to produce desired outcomes in terms of student learning, development, and achievement. It involves the school's capacity to efficiently utilize its resources, implement effective teaching strategies, and create a positive learning environment. School

Comparative Analysis Between Quality ... (Akinsola & Saidu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408209>

efficacy" refers to the belief or perception that a school, as a whole, has the capacity to successfully achieve its goals and objectives. It involves the collective confidence of the school community—administrators, teachers, students, and sometimes parents in the school's ability to create a positive and effective learning environment. This concept is often associated with the broader field of school effectiveness, which examines the factors that contribute to a school's success in promoting student learning and development. School efficacy is closely related to the concept of self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's belief in their own ability to succeed in specific situations. In the context of schools, the collective self-efficacy of the school community can significantly impact the overall effectiveness of the educational institution. Researchers often explore school efficacy in the context of school improvement efforts and interventions to enhance educational outcomes for students.

Quality assurance in education aims at preventing quality problems and ensures that the products of the school system conform to the expected standard. According to Okebukola (2017), quality assurance is an umbrella concept for a host of activities that are designed to improve the quality of input, process and output of an education system. Omopariola (2017) argues that quality assurance is the steady maintenance and improvement of the quality or standard of education in all areas of the school system. In Nigeria, secondary education prepares students for useful living within the society and preparing them for higher education. It is very pivotal in the educational system of the country because it is the bedrock which determines the academic and professional career of students. It is also of six-year duration comprising of three years each for junior and senior secondary school levels. In spite of the importance of secondary education system, concerns about the poor quality of secondary education graduates are on increase in Nigeria (Adeyemi & Adeyemi, 2020). For instance, the growing complaints by parents, heads of tertiary education institutions and the employers indicate that secondary school graduates are poorly prepared for the challenges ahead of them. Reporting on obstacles bedeviling the secondary schools' effectiveness, Abenga (2019), maintained that concerns expressed by government bureaucrats, politicians and the public in general is over what they perceived as lack of and/or inadequate quality assurance practices in secondary schools. Also, Olaleye and Jolaoso (2017) reported that the present state of achievement of secondary school students as measured by performance in external examination conducted by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) has been characterized by a declining trend, which caused a dissatisfaction of the general public.

In the North West zone of Nigeria, as in other geo-political zone of the country, inadequate quality assurance poses a serious challenge to school effectiveness of secondary schools. Thus, according to Ekundayo (2018), the ineffectiveness of the secondary schools in the three domains of learning has been attributed to several factors such as parental factor, teacher factor, societal factors and institutional factors. While the institutional factor considered here relates to the quality assurance mechanisms such as instructional supervision, in-service training and the learning environment that were put in place in the school system. In the same tone, Adeyemi & Adeyemi (2020) observed that the maintenance of factors such as curriculum, instructional materials, equipment, school management, teacher training and resources are some of the indicators of quality education. Quality assurance therefore has to do with compliance with standards set in ensuring that schools achieve the objectives for which they are established.

Instructional supervision as a key factor of quality mechanism in the school system is a service activity designed to help teachers do their job better so as to bring about effective operation of a good system. According Walker (2016) instructional supervision is a task of improving instruction through regular monitoring of teachers. The implication of this definition is that, a deficiency in this exercise may spell doom for the education system. Series of concerns has been raised over the level of both internal and external supervision in secondary schools in North-West geo-political zone of Nigeria. It appears that the principals of schools and heads of departments who are in charge of internal supervision are being found wanting in their assignments. Inadequate or haphazard supervision could result in teachers' lackadaisical attitude towards their job and consequently make school ineffective. Usman (2015) found a positive relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' performance and academic achievements of students in secondary schools. This in extension has implication for secondary schools' effectiveness.

In-service training is another factor of quality assurance mechanism that has impact on the level of effectiveness of a school. In-service training is an on-the-job training organized for teachers to help them develop their skills in their areas of discipline. It can be in the form of training organized by the agencies in charge of the school system in order to improve the professional development of the teachers. Contrary to studies of (Garba, 2014; Rahman, Jamani, Akhter, Chisthi, & Ajmal, 2015), which revealed positive relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness. There are evidences such as Alabi, (2016), Adeyemi, et al, (2019), Akomo, et al (2015) that revealed that some practicing teachers in secondary schools were not adequately equipped with the necessary skills for curriculum delivery. They emphasize that some do not know how well to present lessons in the classroom. Besides, few teachers that know how to identify relevant instructional materials do

Comparative Analysis Between Quality ... (Akinsola & Saidu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408209>

not know how to make effective use of the instructional materials. All these explained why performance of the secondary school teachers is declining and thus making the schools to be ineffective.

Another factor of quality assurance that could affect school effectiveness is learning environment. According to Omopariola (2017) learning can occur anywhere, but the positive learning outcomes generally sought by educational systems happen in quality learning environment. Thus, conduciveness of the school learning environment has been said to be potent factors influencing students' achievements in the three domains of learning and thereby result to school effectiveness. This view was also supported by many studies, for example, Etim, Iya, Akuegwu, Basil, Uchendu & Chika, (2019) that found positive relationship between school facilities and school effectiveness in the environment of learning while, Ogunode, & Agwor, (2020) also reiterated provision of adequate facilities for effective teaching and learning to take place.

In the dynamic landscape of secondary school education, the co-relationships between quality assurance mechanisms and administration play a pivotal role in shaping the overall educational experience. While quality assurance mechanisms are designed to ensure and enhance the educational standards, administrative practices act as the backbone of school management. However, there is a gap in our understanding of how these two crucial elements interact and influence each other in the context of secondary education. This research aims to delve into the complexities of this relationship, seeking to identify the key factors that contribute to effective co-ordination or potential conflicts between quality assurance mechanisms and administration at the secondary school level. By addressing this gap, the study seeks to provide insights that can inform policy decisions, improve educational practices, and contribute to the overall advancement of secondary education systems.

Objectives of the Study

This study was designed to investigate co-relationships between quality assurance mechanisms and administration at secondary school level of education in North-west, Nigeria. Specifically; the objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To determine the nature of the relationship between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria.
2. To examine the significance of the relationship existing between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the nature of the relationship between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary school effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?
2. Is there any significant relationship between Quality Assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?

Methodology

The design of this study was basically correlation type of research design. The population of the study consisted of 26,048 teachers from all the senior secondary schools in the North West zone of Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. These schools cut across Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara States in the North-West geo-political zones of Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure technique was used to select the sample. The first stage involved the use of purposive sampling to select four States due to security situations out of the seven states in North-west Nigeria. The states selected were Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano and katsina. For the second stage, a proportionate stratified random sampling procedure was used to determine the number of schools per state. Fifteen (15) schools were selected from Jigawa State, twenty (20) schools each from Kaduna, Kano and katsina States respectively to make up total number of Seventy-Five (75) secondary schools used for the study. The third and final stage involved the use of simple random sampling to select 20 teachers from each of the 75 senior secondary schools, making 1500 teachers in all.

Three instruments were used to gather the data for the study. The first instrument was tagged Quality Assurance Mechanism Questionnaire (QAMQ) and it comprises two sections. Section A elicited response on personal background information of the respondents while section B requested information about the influence of quality assurance mechanisms on administration of secondary school effectiveness. The second instrument which was tagged School Effectiveness Questionnaire (SEQ), also consisted of two sections A and B. Section A of the questionnaire elicited information on school variables such as location, type and level. Section B requested information about the influence of quality assurance mechanisms on affective and

Comparative Analysis Between Quality ... (Akinsola & Saidu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408209>

psychomotor domains of learning activities in the schools. The third instrument used for the study was a Qualifying Examinations results. It measured the students' performance which is also a factor of teachers' contribution to administration of secondary school effectiveness. Hence, this result was combined to the results of the analysis of the responses on Section B of the School Effectiveness Questionnaire (SEQ) to determine the administration of secondary school efficacy. Both (QAMQ) and (SEQ) instruments were structured along five point likert scale namely Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 5,4, 3, 2 and 1 point respectively positively demanding statement and reverse for the negative ones. The teachers who are the respondents were requested to indicate the extent of their agreement or disagreement with each item in the questionnaires. The instruments were validated by research experts in Educational Management, and Tests and Measurement in Bayero University Kano. The QAMQ and SEQ instruments were validated, and test-retest method of reliability was used to determine their reliability coefficients of 0.78 and 0.81 respectively were obtained using test-retest method. The data for the study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive used include frequency counts and percentage score, while the inferential statistics used was Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Result

Research Question 1

What is the nature of the relationship between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary school effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?

Table 1: Intercorrelation Matrix of Independent Variables (Quality Assurance Mechanisms) and Dependent Variables (School effectiveness)

Variables	Quality Assurance Mechanisms			School Effectiveness
	1	2	3	4
1	1.000			
2	.492	1.000		
3	.528	.420	1.000	
4	0.745	0.682	0.825	1.000

Key: 1 = Instructional supervision; 2 = In-service training;
 3 = Learning environment; 4 = School effectiveness.

Table 1 shows the intercorrelation matrix with the coefficient of correlation for each pair of the variables examined. The findings of the correlation matrix show the nature of the relationship between pairs of quality assurance mechanisms' variables ((instructional supervision, in-service training and learning environment) with respect to administration of secondary school's efficacy's variables (school effectiveness). The results presented in Table 1 shows that there existed positive correlation between quality assurance mechanisms' variables: instructional supervision (0.745), in-service training (0.682) and Learning environment (0.825) and school effectiveness.

Research Question 2:

Is there any significant relationship between Quality Assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis of Pairs of Quality Assurance Mechanisms and administration of secondary School Effectiveness

Variable	No. of Cases	Calculated r_{xy}	Critical r_{xy}	Decision at $P < .05$
Instructional supervision (x) School Effectiveness (y)	1500	0.745*	0.250	S
In-service Training (x) School Effectiveness (y)	1500	0.682*	0.250	S

Comparative Analysis Between Quality ... (Akinsola & Saidu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408209>

Learning Environment (x)				
School Effectiveness (y)	1500	0.825*	0.250	S

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

The results of the correlation coefficient analysis presented in Table 2 show that there exists a significant relationship between quality assurance mechanism of instructional supervision and administration of secondary school effectiveness (calculated $r_{xy} = 0.745$; critical $r_{xy} = 0.250$); a significant relationship between quality assurance mechanism of in-service training and administration of secondary school effectiveness (calculated $r_{xy} = 0.682$; critical $r_{xy} = 0.250$); and a significant relationship between quality assurance mechanism of learning environment and administration of secondary school effectiveness (calculated $r_{xy} = 0.825$; critical $r_{xy} = 0.250$).

Discussions of the Findings

The findings presented in Table 4.1 revealed that positive relationship exist between relationship between quality assurance mechanisms (Instructional supervision (0.745), In-service training (0.682) and Learning environment (0.825)) and administration of secondary school effectiveness. The observations from this study indicated that quality assurance mechanisms are strongly related to administration of secondary school effectiveness. Hence, each of the quality assurance mechanisms has strong relative effect on administration of secondary school effectiveness. There are some earlier studies that supported the findings here. Usman (2015) for instance, investigated the impact of instructional supervision on academic performance of secondary school students (a factor of school effectiveness) in Nasarawa State. He found a positive relationship between instructional supervision and school effectiveness. This implies that if instructions are well supervised through regular monitoring of teachers, improved school effectiveness will be the result. For the impact of in-service training on the level of effectiveness of a school, studies of Rahman et. al, (2015) and Garba, (2014) revealed positive relationship between the two variables. This present study therefore confirmed that if in-service training is provided for teachers, it will help in developing their skills in their area of discipline. The teachers will know how well to deliver their lessons and how to make effective use of instructional materials, thus making schools effective. While for the relationship between learning environment and school effectiveness, Walker, (2016) and Omopariola, (2017) in their different studies found positive relationship existing between learning environment and school effectiveness. Their findings revealed learning environment to be a potent factor influencing school effectiveness.

In seeking answer to the second research question that says: Is there any significant relationship between Quality Assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary schools effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria? The study reveals that there is significant relationship between the pairs of quality assurance mechanisms (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary school effectiveness. The implication of these findings, for instance on the significant relationship between instructional supervision and administration of secondary school effectiveness is that effective supervision of the teachers' activities will invariably lead to effective administration of secondary school effectiveness. The reason for this is due to the fact that the secondary school principals and Heads of Department who are the supervisory agencies are up and doing in the schools. This finding thus, corroborates a similar study of Usman (2015), Alonge & Obiweluzor, (2015) and Walker (2016). Also, the significant relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness implies that if enough provision is made for teachers' in-service training and teachers are encouraged to attend, school effectiveness will be enhanced. This finding could also due to the fact that teachers' attendance and participation in various in-service training will bring about sustainable human capacity development which will invariably contribute to school effectiveness. This finding is in consonance with Garba, (2014), Rahman et. al (2015) and Omopariola (2017). While the observed significant relationship between learning environment and school effectiveness suggests that when the learning environment is conducive, when all learning resources are better put in place and well utilized by the teachers, better performance (factor of school effectiveness) are expected from the students. Hence, enhanced school effectiveness will be the result. This also suggests that learning environment has great influence on school effectiveness. This finding is in agreement with similar findings of Ahunanya & Ubabudu (2016) and Omopariola (2017). More so, this also agrees with the studies of Asiabaka (2018) and Adeyemi & Adeyemi (2020) that found positive relationship between school facilities and school effectiveness in the environment of learning.

Conclusion

Comparative Analysis Between Quality ... (Akinsola & Saidu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408209>

Based on the findings of this study, the conclusion drawn was that quality assurance mechanisms such as instructional supervision, in-service training, and learning environment has positive relationship to the effectiveness of the administration of secondary schools in Northwest, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The Secondary School Principals and Heads of Departments as quality assurance agents should sustain the tempo of instructional supervision in schools in order to ensure better administration of secondary school effectiveness.
2. Secondary school principals should encourage teachers to attend and participate in-service training such as workshops, seminars and conferences. This is to enhance better human capital development and to improve upon the level of school effectiveness.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the teachers and schools that have played a significant role in the completion of this research paper. We are deeply indebted to the principals of the sampled schools for their unwavering support throughout the entire data collection process. Their contributions have been instrumental in shaping the direction and quality of this work. We also extend our appreciation to the editorial committee members of ZIJE for their constructive feedback, scholarly input, and time devoted to reviewing and enhancing the content of this document.

References

- Abenga, E. (2019). Impact of School Requirements on Pupils' Academic Performance. *Journal of education and Development*,3(1:176).
- Adeyemi, J.K., Salami, I.O, Ajadi, T.O. (2021). Institutional Factors and Student Records Management Practices In South-West Nigerian University Registries, *GOJAMSS JOURNAL*, 21(2021)
- Adeyemi, S. B & Adeyemi, O. O. (2020). Teachers' Perception of Implementation of Quality Assurance on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Ilesa West Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. *Kampala International University (KIU) Journal of Humanities*, 5(2): 183-188. Kampala.
- Ahunanya, S. L. & Ubabudu, M. C. (2016). Enrolment, facilities and financial allocation in Lagos higher education: Implication for quality graduates. *Nigeria Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (NAEAP)*, 6(1), 153-164.
- Akomo, O., Ajowi, J.O. & Bosire, J. (2015) Factors limiting the usage of ICT in the delivery of management services in public secondary schools in Siaya country. *Mediterranean Journal of social sciences*.
- Alabi, T. A. (2006). *The use of computer in educational management* Codat publication.
- Alonge, H. O. & Obiweluzor, N. (2015). Strategies for managing indiscipline among secondary school students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Foundations and Management*. 9(1), 77-85.
- Asiabaka, I. P. (2018): The Need for Effective Facility Management in Schools in Nigeria. *NewYork Science of Journal: Retrieved from <http://www.sciencepub.org>, SSN 154- 0200*
- Ekundayo, Oluwayomi A. Mr. (2018) "The Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance in Selected Insurance Companies in Nigeria.," *International Journal of African Development: Vol. 5: Iss. 1, Article 5*.
- Etim, Iya E, Akuegwu, Basil A, and Uchendu, Chika C. (2019), Assessment of Quality Assurance Practices in Colleges of Education in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, Nigeria. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.2, No.1, 94-105.
- Garba, A. (2014). Secondary education in Nigeria: A synthesis of basic student specific concerns from guidance and counselling perspectives. *Journal of International Cooperation in Education*, 15(2), 195-205.
- Mensah, J. K., Okyere M. and Kuranchie, A. (2013). Student attitude towards Mathematics and performance: Does the teacher attitude matter? , ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.4, No.3, 2013
- Ogunode, N. J., & Agwor, N. O. (2020). Administration Teacher Education in Nigeria: Problem and Suggestion. *Journal of Applied and Theoretical Social Sciences*, 2(4), 29-41. <https://doi.org/10.37241/jatss.2020.17>

Comparative Analysis Between Quality ... (Akinsola & Saidu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408209>

- Okebukola, P. (2017). Higher Education Systems and Institutions in Nigeria. Encyclopedia of International Higher Education and Institutions in Nigeria, first online 22 December, 2016.
- Okeke-James, N. J., Igbokwe, I. C., Anyanwu, J. A., & Ogbo, R. N. (2020). Quality assurance in secondary education for socio-economic development in Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 7(5), 175-185.
- Olaleye, T. M. & Jolaoso, A. T. (2017). Teachers' quality and students' learning outcome in secondary schools in FCT, Abuja. *International Journal of Educational Foundations and Management*, 11(1), 51-56.
- Omopariola, O. F. (2017) Quality assurance and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Unpublished M.Ed. thesis submitted to the Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti.
- Rahman, F., Jumani, N.B., Akhter, Y., Christhi, S. H., & Ajmal, M. (2015). Relationship between training of teachers and effective teaching. *International Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 150-156.
- Scheerens, J. (2016). Theories of educational effectiveness and ineffectiveness. A critical review of the knowledge based, p259-289
- Smith, J. A. (2021). Enhancing Education Access in Developing Countries: A Case Study of Policy Interventions (Working Paper No. 5678). World Bank.
- Usman, Y. D. (2015). The impact of instructional supervision on academic performance of secondary school students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(10), 160-167
- Walker, J. W. (2016). Supervision of instruction and school management. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Co.